

Our Courageous Faith: Walking Together Heart-in-Heart

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Introduction

This is possibly the first time in many centuries when the whole world is challenged as challengingly as now. At this point in the history of the world, the so-called rich nations and the so-called poor nations are all in the same boat trying to row to the shore. Now the elite and rich even within a nation are on the same level as the poorest of the poor. Those in high-rises are equal to those who live in hovels, slums and on the streets. Those with luxurious accommodations and who earn six and even seven figures salaries per month are on the same level as those who have nowhere to lay their heads and who may not even have a square meal a day.

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However, the Caronavirus which causes COVID-19, has taught us many lessons. The most striking of them all has been a stark and grim reminder of the fact that after all is said and done, we are only mortal. This lesson which ought to have been evident and obvious was definitely not. Many of us thought (and some possibly still do) that we were/are invincible. We could do what we wanted, live as we wanted to and nothing and no one could touch us or wake us up from our complacency. The Caronavirus intervened and put a stop to this way of thinking, albeit temporarily (because history has taught us that we do not learn

life's lessons as we ought to). The Caronavirus has indeed been a great leveller.

Treatise on Faith in Hebrews Chapter 11

“Now faith is the assurance (reality) of things hoped for, the conviction (proof) of things not seen.” (Heb 11:1)

- a. In an attempt to respond to the present situation in which we find ourselves, we can turn to what the letter to the Hebrews says about faith in Chapter 11 of that same letter. It defines faith in the following words, “Now faith is the assurance (reality) of things hoped for, the conviction (proof) of things not seen.” (Heb 11:1). It goes on to detail the faith of Abel, Enoch and Noah and then elaborates on the faith of Abraham. This faith is explained from three points of view. These are: God’s promise to Abram¹ of (1) land (Gen 12:1-3; 13:14-15,17; 15:18;), (2) progeny (Gen 13:16; 15:5; 17:4-8, 15-16,19; 18:10; 21:3; 22:17) and (3) the sacrifice of his son Isaac (22:1-10).
- b. In the first case, Abram did indeed have land and become prosperous according to the promise of the Lord. However, he did not let his prosperity get the better of him. This is seen in his generosity to let his nephew Lot have the first choice of which land he wanted to possess (Gen 13:8-12). This generosity on the part of Abram resulted in God being even more generous with him (Gen 13:14-18). Though there were moments in Abram’s life when he faltered (Gen 15:3; 17:17; 18:12), these were brief. For the most part, he believed and “the Lord reckoned it to him as righteousness (Gen 15:6). Though he was landless and advanced in age, because he did what God commanded him to do and did it with faith, he was blessed beyond his own expectations with both land and progeny (Gen 17:5; Gen 21:1-7; 24:34-36). However, even as he received blessings in abundance from God, he was

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asked to give up or sacrifice his son (Gen 22:1-2), who would be the one who would continue his blood line. When Abraham listened

to this command of God, he shows no surprise whatever nor does he raise any objection. He obeys because he has faith that whatever God does will be for his good and God’s glory. As a matter of fact, so great is Abraham’s faith in God’s word that he even makes up an answer (Gen 22:8) to his son’s question about the offering (Gen 22:7). The result of his willingness to obey the voice of God and do God’s will in faith results in God responding to him with generosity that only God is capable of (Gen 22:15-18).

- c. The catalogue of faith continues with the faith of the parents of Moses (Heb 11:23) and then of Moses himself (Heb 11:24-28). It begins with God’s providential care of Moses right from his birth (Ex 2:1-10) till the time he could be God’s instrument (Ex 3:7-12) in redeeming the people from slavery and oppression to freedom and blessing (Ex 14:30-31)². However, it was not easy for Moses to undertake to be God’s prophet. From when he approached Pharaoh (who refused to listen to Moses or relent) (Ex 5:1-2, 23; 7:13-16, 22-23; 8:15,19,32; 9:7,12,35; 10:20,27) till even after accompanying the people back to the Promised Land (who kept complaining against both Moses and Aaron) (5: 20-23; 6:9; 17:1-7), Moses has tremendous challenges when he obeyed God’s word and acted as God wanted him to. Yet, he persevered. Though he was not privileged to see the Promised Land (Deut 32:52; 34:4), he did not give up the mission entrusted to him and persevered to the very end (Deut 34:5).

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d. The eulogy continues by mentioning six individuals in the later history of Israel (Heb 11:32) who may have been considered heroes in Israel's history.³ Of

these, four are judges (Gideon, Barak, Samson and Jephthah), one a king (David) and one a prophet (Samuel).⁴ In this summary, we are presented with what was accomplished through their faith. In each of those mentioned, they did obtain the promises that were made to them.⁵

e. However, even as the treatise on faith continues, we are told of those who had to undergo great ordeal and suffer much with no indication of an end in sight. It seems that besides having Eleazar (2 Macc 6:18-31) and the Maccabean brothers in mind (2 Macc 7:1-42) the author would also have had prophets like Elijah, Elisha, Zechariah, Jeremiah and Isaiah in mind. The trials that all of these had to face was because of their fidelity and their firm conviction that they were doing what God had called them to do.

f. The treatise ends with an affirmation of faith in God's word. Though it seemed on the surface level that many of those who did God's will, did not receive their just reward, they in fact did receive something much better than they expected. This is why we are called despite evidence to the contrary to believe even when we cannot see and even when we do not see. We are called to do what we have to do in every present moment and persevere in our faith in imitation of Jesus himself who is the pioneer and perfecter of faith (Heb 12:1-3).

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Our Response

In connection with the treatise in Hebrews, how do we respond with faith in the situation in which we find ourselves?

The Caronavirus has brought the whole world to its knees. No matter how advanced our Science and Technology is, we find that at this moment we are helpless. Even now, it is not clear how the virus originated, how it spreads (all that we have now are a variety of theories), how it can be controlled (isolation from others is considered safer than contact, but whether the infection can be caused from surfaces is another matter) and how we must respond to the situation and life. It is estimated that it may take eighteen months and more to find a cure for this viral infection.

Our response cannot be on merely the individual level, but also has to be at the National/International levels. We now have to think globally and act both globally and locally. This is how I suggest we can do that:

On the Individual Level

a. Positive Thinking and Positive Actions

One response to the fact that the Caronavirus is spreading so rapidly is to throw in the towel, to give up and give in. It is to allow negative thinking, emotions and feelings to rise to the surface of one's consciousness and so to despair. It can also be to see the present situation as the wrath of God⁶ and therefore blame God or accuse God of not caring.⁷

Another response is to think positively, creatively and constructively. These positive thoughts will express themselves in positive feelings and actions. I do believe that these positive responses will not only improve the atmosphere in one's home but will also go beyond one's home to others. The way to do this is to start each day with a positive affirmation of oneself, others and the world. Self-

talk is a great help in this regard. We keep telling ourselves that things will get better and that God is still in control. We continue to focus on the little things no matter how small. We thank God that we have the facilities we have like water, food, a mobile phone which allows us to stay in touch with others and the world, internet facilities and so many things we usually have taken for granted. We can thank God for the peace and quiet that we are experiencing and that the quality of the air we breathe has improved so considerably. We thank God that we are able to breathe without impediment or difficulty. We thank God that we are getting more rest now than we ever did in the recent past. We thank God that there are so many selfless doctors, nurses and medical personnel who are working hard to help others. We thank God for those who are toiling to research a cure for this virus. We thank God for giving us an opportunity to thank him. We can use the extra time we have to always do the things we wanted to but never found the time to do them. If we are blessed with Internet facility, we can learn a new language or skill. We can simply be content with spending time with the members of our family.

b. Live in the Present Moment

One of the most challenging things for us to do is to live in the present moment. We often have regrets about the past or are obsessed with the future. Consequently we do not live in the present moment and it passes us by. This is time like no other to simply be in the NOW. In reality, there is no next moment or tomorrow. The present moment is all we have and will ever have. Today is indeed the tomorrow we worried about yesterday. Now is the later and later is now.

c. Exercise

In order for our minds to be fresh our bodies must also be fresh. This is an excellent time for regular and dedicated exercise. One does not need to have too much space for

exercise.

Depending on one's age and health, one can choose that exercise that suits one best.

d. Reconnect

This is also a time to renew old friendships and strengthen relationships. While it is not possible to have physical contact because of social distancing it does not mean that our hearts have to be far from each other. For those who are blessed with mobile and smartphones, it is fairly easy to get in touch with others who also have the same facility.

e. Meditate/Pray

Prayer and Meditation are a great way to relieve stress and to connect with God. There are a variety of ways to pray. One of these is verbal prayer (reciting the name of God or an attribute of God over and over again, reading a text from scripture and seeing how it applies to my life or reciting a popular prayer by rote, but stopping after each phrase or sentence to see how I can apply it to my present situation). Another way is without words. I simply become aware of the breath that I take in, which I hold in my lung and which I exhale. When I am breathing in, I think only of the positive.

Deeds in this context are: providing to researchers the best facilities and conditions in which to do the required research (in this context generosity is needed from the ones who have), ensuring that the poor, elderly, differently abled and all marginalized groups are looked after and provided for, giving to doctors and medical personnel as much support as possible in terms of acknowledgement of their services, providing the rest they require and looking after their needs.

It is this is hold within my lungs. When I breathe out, I exhale all that is negative and noxious within me. Yet another way is to use the four fingers and thumb of one's hands to pray. I begin with the thumb and pray those who are closest to me (the members of my family, my friends, my relatives, a loved one who is sick or going through some turmoil at this time). I can bring each member and ask for a special grace for them. I then move to the pointer. Here I pray for those who point the way. These could be religious leaders, teachers, mentors, guides and others who have shown me the way to what is good. When I come to the tallest finger, I pray for world leaders (Presidents/Prime Ministers/Chancellors of countries/other leaders) that they be blessed with wisdom to lead their nations individually and co-operate with each other at this challenging time. The ring finger is the weakest finger. Here, I bring those who are not as fortunate as I. These will include the millions in every country who are homeless and live from one meal to the next, those who do not know where their next meal is coming from or where they will sleep at night, those who have no one with whom they can share if they have a toothache or headache, those who are shunned and driven away because they are suspect and those whom nobody cares about or even notices. Finally, when I come to the little finger I pray for myself. I ask for the grace to keep living a life of gratitude and a live in the present.

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f. Reach out to Someone in Need

Often, we get so caught up in our own small selfish worlds that we have no time to even think about the challenges that others go through. If there is an elderly or differently abled person, can I reach out to him/her in some small way?

g. Faith

In the context of the definition and catalogue of faith given by Hebrews 11 and also that things did not always happen

the way they were expected to, we are called to a faith that believes without seeing and even to a faith that believes even when it does not see. If one was able to see before believing, it would not require faith of any kind. However, in the present situation, to have faith is indeed a challenge. There seems to be no respite to the plight of the whole world. A cure seems so far away. How can we believe that this is for the good of each one of us and for the good of the world? Abram was landless, advanced in age and did not have progeny. God told Abram what he had to do, Abram did it (Gen 12:4) and became Abraham (Gen 17:5). Moses was diffident (Ex 4:1; 6:12), he was not eloquent and slow of speech and slow of tongue (Ex 4:10), yet he did as God commanded him and though he did not see the promised land, he did succeed in leading the people out of Egypt (Deut 34:4). Through these examples and others enumerated by the letter to the Hebrews here, we are called to continue to do what we have to do and obey the commands of the Lord. It is likely that like Abram, we may be blessed to see the cure in the immediate future and so experience our own becoming Abraham. It is also likely that like Moses the cure might come after the Lord calls us to himself. Be that as it may, our response is to continue to have faith and to continue to believe. This means to be sure that the reality we hope for will become real and the conviction that even though we cannot see, God will make a way.

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On the National and International Levels

a. Sharing Information in an Open Manner

Though each national government will be concerned about its own people first, the world leaders must also realise that

this is a universal not national or parochial challenge. This is why the approach to this challenge must be universal. We have long since realise

that our world is indeed a global village and now is the time to put that realization in action. We use the advances in science and technology to reach out to each other with information, resources and even funds if needed. It is the need of the hour to get rid of our selfish and narrow-minded way of proceeding and put the needs of the whole of humanity before everything else. Now is not the time for world leaders to try and score brownie points or to get popularity votes. Now is the time for magnanimity and large-heartedness. Now is the time for generosity and thinking and acting globally and universally.

b. Keeping the Populace Informed

The larger majority of the people are not aware of the intricacies of the problem that we are facing. As a matter of fact, even experts in the medical profession are still groping in the dark. In a situation like this it is important for world leaders to inspire confidence in their citizens. This they can do by regularly giving out information through whichever means they can to even those who live in the remotest part of their respective countries. When information is given by someone in authority, it is more easily believed than otherwise. In order to do this the services of medical experts could be used so that correct information and not myths are disseminated as much as is possible.

c. Love over Fear

In order to ensure that instructions about lockdown and other measures are followed, governments use a variety of measures. Some of these are violent and involve the use of physical force. It is a proven fact that while force does work

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temporarily to ensure discipline the effects are temporary and in most instances, obedience is out of fear and not conviction.⁸ If governments take steps to educate the people as best they can (using the expertise of renowned medical personnel and other knowledgeable persons) and appeal to deeper values like care for oneself and the other, generosity, altruism and above all love, it will have a more lasting effect.

d. Turn to God

God is known by different names and worshipped differently in different religions and cultures. In some cultures, God is not acknowledged and worship of God is not allowed or approved. The noun "God" is not a name for God. It may be translated as 'Supreme Being', or 'Divine Being' or any other name that one prefers. We have to understand with our minds and hearts that God is God and we must let God be God. We also have to know that though we sometimes like to think that we are god and like to play god, we are humans. And if there was any doubt before this pandemic that we as humans are supreme, it is quite certain that all doubt is removed now. We are vulnerable, we are weak, we are fragile and we are dust. If we understand and accept this and if we acknowledge that we do not know, it will be the beginning of wisdom. This is why we turn to God. God is beyond all names and forms. God is beyond anything that we can say or think about God. What we need to do is turn in all humility and nothingness and ask God for help. Acknowledging our dependence on God is the first step toward humility. While the situation might not be like that

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of Sodom and Gomorrah, the petitionary prayer of Abraham that God relent, is a pointer as to how we can pray (Gen 18:23-33). It also indicates who God is and who we are. We are (whether we acknowledge it or not) at God's mercy.

e. Faith

Over all the above, we must put on faith⁹. As Chapter 11 of the letter to the Hebrews so eloquently describes it, faith is a necessary element for every one of us as we struggle with this incomprehensible pandemic. The example of the exemplars of faith must spur us on. This faith is not merely intellectual assent, but an active faith which shows itself in deeds.¹⁰ Deeds in this context are: providing to researchers the best facilities and conditions in which to do the required research (in this context generosity is needed from the ones who have), ensuring that the poor, elderly, differently abled and all marginalized groups are looked after and provided for, giving to doctors and medical personnel as much support as possible in terms of acknowledgement of their services, providing the rest they require and looking after their needs of food and other basic amenities and assuring the populace at regular intervals that all that is necessary is being done and then turning to God with hope and faith.

Conclusion

The call to each one of us as we struggle to come to terms with the aftermath of the havoc caused by the novel Coronavirus is to remember that we are one human family. The virus makes no distinction whatever between rich and poor, male and female, black, brown, yellow or white. It treats all equally and infects all in a very similar manner. In like manner we too are called to journey with each other as companions and comrades on this journey of life. While we might not be able to walk hand-in-hand at this moment we can definitely walk together heart-in-heart.

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¹ Abram is Abram which is translated as “exalted ancestor” till God tells him that he will no longer be called Abram but “Abraham” which means “ancestor of a multitude”. “No longer shall your name be Abram, but your name shall be Abraham; for I have made you the ancestor of a multitude of nations.” (Gen 17:5)

² A full account of how Moses became God's instrument may be read in Ex 5-12. Moses' perseverance is noteworthy. Though he tries to reason with Pharaoh and appeal to him humbly, Pharaoh will not heed. Despite this, however, Moses does not give up but perseveres.

³ See Attridge, Harold, W., *Hebrews: A Commentary on the Epistle to the Hebrews*, Hermeneia, 1989

⁴ For the correct chronological list see Judges 4-16; 1 Sam 1 and 1 Sam 16

⁵ For the fulfillment of promises to Barak see Judg 5:1-7; Gideon (Judg 6:11-16); Jephthah (Judg 11:29-35); Samson (Judg 13:25); and David (2 Sam 5:19)

⁶ Jesus' response in Lk 13:1-9 is instructive in this regard. When Jesus is told about the Galileans who were slaughtered by Pilate (possibly because they had revolted against the Romans) in the temple so that their blood was mingled with the blood of the animals who had also been slaughtered for sacrifice in the Temple, Jesus responds by stating that tragedy or catastrophe (like we are now experiencing) is not the measure of the sinfulness of the world or even of one's need to repent. He goes on to give the example of a natural tragedy (the collapse of the Tower of Siloam) to make the same point but also to state emphatically that everyone needs to repent or look at life anew.

⁷ In Mk 4:35-40, the miracle of the storm on the lake, the disciples accuse Jesus of just such an attitude when they ask “Teacher, do you not care that we are perishing?” (Mk 4:38). Jesus, however, will point to their fear and lack of faith and is surprised by it (Mk 4:40).

⁸ See Desiree Rumbagh, <https://www.desireerumbaugh.com/love-is-stronger-than-fear-2/>; see also Michael Braunstein, *Love vs. Fear* <https://thereader.com/heartland-healing/the-two-emotions-love-vs-fear>, Ben Irwin, *Proving Love is stronger than Fear: Summer's Campaign*,